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Reduction of Farmers Marketing Risks Through Regulation

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Introduction

Change is the need of Hour & to improve the market system of farm products, wholesale agricultural produce markets began to be regulated in the 1950s and 1960s. Based on the Model Act circulated by the central government, almost all major states (27) enacted APMR legislation. This legislation covers 7161 markets, which cover more than 98% of the identified wholesale markets in the country.

Priority Areas in Agricultural Marketing

Various studies on the impact of regulated markets (Acharya, 1985, 1998; Aggarwal and Meena, 1997; and Suryawanashi *et al.*, 1995) have highlighted several positive features of the regulation program. These include a visibly open process of price discovery, more accurate and reliable weighing, standardized market charges, payment of cash to farmers without undue deductions, dispute settlement mechanism, timing and sequencing of auctions, reduction in physical losses of produce, and availability of several amenities in market yards.

Regulation of Agricultural Produce Markets

In the emerging scenario, however, the relevance of the market regulation program seems to have declined. A comprehensive study of the agricultural marketing system during the last five years by Acharya (2004) identifies several problems associated with regulated markets. For example, since the Agricultural Produce Marketing Committees (APMCs) do not allow the traders to buy from the farmers outside the specified market yards or sub-yards, the cost of marketing increases. Also, the area served per market yard is high, the national average being 459 sq. km., and considerably higher in states like Assam, Himachal Pradesh, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan. The long travel distance involved to reach a marketplace is a disincentive for most farmers, with small surplus to sell. Several markets are also poorly equipped. Apart from the primary assembling markets, there are 27,294 rural periodic markets, where small and marginal farmers and livestock owners come in contact with the market economy. Most of these (85%) have not been developed, which hinders the market orientation of rural areas. In several states, since election of APMCs are not regularly held, they are superseded by the governments and administered by bureaucrats, depriving them of the characteristic of being farmer-dominated managerial bodies. The staff remains overly occupied with the collection of market fee and construction work rather than market development. Congestion in the market

yards delays the disposal of the farmers' produce, frustrating the farmers. In several markets, malpractices by traders persist, such as late payment, deduction for cash or spot payment, and non-issue of sale slips. In some markets, market functionaries (traders, commission agents, and laborers) have formed strong associations, barricading the entry of new functionaries. A considerable part of the market fee, which by definition is the charge for the services provided to market functionaries, is not plowed back. In some states, this has even become source of revenue for the government. By and large, APMCs have emerged as some sort of government-sponsored monopolies in the supply of marketing services/facilities, with all the drawbacks and inefficiency associated with public sector monopolies.

The Model Act is comprehensive. When adopted, it will improve the efficiency of the marketing system and encourage private sector investment in agricultural marketing but both state governments and traders/commission agents are resisting its adoption. Only a few states have adopted the model, and that partially. State APMCs fear losing market free if alternative markets are established. Traders/commission agents fear losing their business/incomes. Several options are available to allay such fears. The contractors (under contract farming) can assure payment of market fee to APMCs. The latter can declare more sub-yards to be managed by cooperatives or private entrepreneurs. In the village sub-yards, private sector companies or associations can create cleaning, sorting, grading and packaging facilities employing rural youth. The traders/commission agents may be persuaded to organise into groups or work as individuals as agents of contractors.

Independent of amendments in state APMR legislation, certain problems in the functioning of AOMCs require immediate attention. These pertain to bureaucratization of market committees, not plowing back market fees for market development, and cartelization of traders and market functionaries. The over emphasis of market committees on collection of market fees rather than promotion of marketing efficiency also needs attention. To this end, the state governments should be persuaded to act on the following lines:

- 1) Holding regular elections of market committees.
- 2) Compulsory plowing back of market fees for development of marketing facilities.
- 3) Liberalization of licensing of traders and market functionaries.
- 4) Promotion of grading, standardization and quality certification.
- 5) Creating cleaning, sorting, grading and packaging facilities in villages and allowing traders to buy in the villages by declaring these places as sub-yards.

Simplification and Rationalization of Regulation Related to Marketing and Food Processing

Apart from the regulation of primary wholesale markets, several other legal instruments were enacted by the central government and the states to influence the conduct of the market (Acharya, 2004; GOI, 2002a). an illustrative list of 222 such enactments is available in Acharya and Agarwal (2004) and GOI

(2002a). Several of these enactments have been repealed, rescinded or lifted during the last five years. There are also at least fourteen enactments governing food-processing activity, administered by fifteen different departments and ministries.

The unfinished agenda of domestic agricultural marketing reforms would need to take the following into account:

- 1) Despite deregulation, small-scale, low-technology firms established under the old restrictive laws still dominate the food processing industry.
- 2) Licensing requirements, stocking limits and movement restrictions for major agricultural products have only been temporarily removed. In some states, these restrictions still prevail in effect. The threat of their reimposition discourages both domestic and foreign investment (Landes and Gulati, 2004).
- 3) Also, restrictions on investment in bulk handling and storage have been removed only temporarily. Though investment incentives have been provided, the private sector is hesitant to invest in bulk handling and storage.
- 4) Despite automatic approval of foreign equity up to 100% in food processing, the multiplicity of food laws hampers the investment potential. The Unified Food Law is yet to be formalized and put in place.
- 5) Restrictions on sale of sugar by sugarcane processors continue, though at a reduced level. The government leveis 10% of the sugar output. The remaining free-sale part is also subjected to controlled release in the market.
- 6) Small- scale reservation on groundnut and mustard processing continues (World Bank, 2004).
- 7) Restrictions on futures trading in livestock products continue (World Bank, 2004).
- 8) Monopsony procurement of raw cotton in Maharashtra is still in place, which hampers free marketing of raw cotton in the country.

The uncertainty created by the unstable regulatory environment has discouraged private sector investment in supporting marketing infrastructure, agro-processing, and agro-industry, that could have expanded demand for primary agricultural products and generated employment in rural areas. The potential for growth in the food processing sub-sector can be exploited by quickly enacting the Unified Food Law. A draft Integrated Food Law is now under the consideration of Palriament. The objective should be to make food laws more industry-friendly and move from multi-level and multi-departmental control to integrated line of command and integrated response to strategic issues, regulations, and eonforcement. Greater reliance needs to be placed on self-compliance by the repealed and several others modified to encourage the growth of the food processing sector, which will help both farmers and consumers.

Withdrawal of restrictions on storage, movement, bulk handling, and other activities being temporary, investment from both domestic and foreign investors is not flowing into the sector. To allay fears of reimposition of such restrictions either the Essential Commodities Act can be replaced with a simplified legislation which empowers the government to impose such restrictions only during an emergency or the withdrawal of restrictions widely publicized to allay investors' wariness.

It is recommended that (a) the provisions in the Draft Food Safety and Standards Bill 2005 (brought out by the Group of Ministers) should be expeditiously passed by Parliament after due consideration; and (b) to allay the fears of reimposition of restrictions, either the Essential Commodities Act should be replaced with simplified legislation, empowering the government to impose such restrictions only during an emergency or the withdrawal of restrictions should be given wide publicity.

Agricultural Price Policy and Food Management

Agricultural price policy has considerably influenced the marketing system of agricultural commodities. The policy was primarily intended to stabilize agricultural prices and influence the price spread from farm gate to the retail level. Its objectives, thrust, and instruments have conspicuously shifted during the last fifty years.

By creating a fairly stable price environment, the policy has been instrumental in inducing the farmers to adopt new production technology and thereby increase output. Geographically dispersed growth of cereal production, coupled with Public Distribution System (PDS) of cereals, helped in increasing physical access to food. Supply of subsidized inputs to farmers and subsidized distribution of foodgrains pushed down the real prices of staple cereals vis-à-vis per capita incomes, which improved economic access to food. These policy measures also enabled the organized sector and industry to keep their wage bills low, as cereals have a considerable weightage in the consumer price index. The benefits of price policy and input/producing farmers deriving their entitlement from production, other farmers who are net purchasers of foodgrains, landless, urban consumers, and industry (Acharya, 1997, 2000).

Even so, some important emerging problems related to agricultural price policy and food management system may be noted:

- 1) During the last six to seven years, the government fixed the Minimum Support Prices (MSPs) of rice and wheat at levels much higher than recommended by the Commission for Agricultural Costs and Prices (CACP) (Acharya and Jogi, 2003). This led to accumulation of excessive stocks and also raised the public cost of foodgrain policy. With coalition governments being the more likely political dispensation in the future, the likelihood of considerations of political economy outweighing rational factors in determining the level of MSPs also increases.
- 2) Foodgrain stocks with the government also increased because of frequent relaxation of Fair Average Quality (FAQ) norms, inappropriate timing of raise in issues price of grains for PDS.

and improper meshing of export-import policy. Currently, however, the stocks are below or close to the minimum prescribed levels.

- 3) For sugarcane, many state governments have been fixing what may be called 'State Advised Prices' (SAP), much higher than the statutory minimum prices fixed by the center. Sometimes the sugar industry finds them unremunerative. SAPs, coupled with the policy of levy on sugar factories, has frequently led to piling up of cane price arrears and ultimately to the phenomenon of sugarcane/sugar cycles in the country.
- 4) Other than in Punjab, Haryana, Western Uttar Pradesh and Andhra Pradesh, price support operations for rice and wheat are not being implemented in some states. A result has been that surpluses have emerged during the last decade, but farmers could not get the MSP for their produce. This happened mainly because the nodal agency (Food Corporation of India, FCI) and state agencies in the new emerging surplus states are not geared to undertake price support operations. The FCI remains occupied with large volumes of purchases in traditional surplus-producing states. Some decentralized procurement and refocusing the operations of FCI to non-traditional states may help in this regard.

One another issue in the context of food management system is the reduction in incentives for private sector participation in foodgrain trade. The price policy and related programs reduced private sector incentives for spatial and temporal arbitrage. For example, for rice and wheat, the intra-year price rice has been considerably lower than the storage cost. It is true that private sector participation in foodgrain trade was reduced due to FCI's operations but FCI's operational costs are not higher. FCI's efficiency vis-à-vis private trade in price support operations and subsequent distribution of foodgrains has been questioned in this context on the ground of its economic cost and consequent outgo on food subsidy. This merits discussion.

First, both the MSP and issue price are determined by the central government. Second, it has been shown (Acharya, 1997) that 71.6% of the FCI's expenditure on procurement and distribution is on items which are determined outside the system. The High Level Committee on Long-Term Grain Policy has put 69% of the economic cost of FCI as policy-induced costs (GOI, 2002b). These include *mandi* charges, purchase/sale tax, cost of gunny bags, interest on working capital, and freight rates. Private trade will also have to incur these costs unless it can evade some of the statutory taxes/charges (Acharya, 1997). Third, losses during storage and transit are estimated at around 1%, which are not unduly high as compared to private channels. Fourth FCI's establishment charges and administrative overheads, estimated to be 2.8% of the economic cost, are not higher than the net margins of private trade. Fifth, a recent study commissioned by the Union Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food and Public Distribution (Chand, 2003) has shown that to attract private trade to buy wheat and paddy from the markets in surplus producing states, the retail prices

during lean months in deficit states ought to rule at more than twice the peak season wheat prices of surplus states. This ratio was estimated as more than three of wheat/rice. These ratios are not less than the ratio of FCI's economic cost wheat/rice to the respective support prices. The findings of the High Level Committee on Long-Term Grain Policy (GOI, 2002b) are on similar lines. The committee has observed that the margin required for private trade to move grain from rural to urban areas of the same state is similar to FCI's distribution margin, which involves an average transport lead of more than 900 km. Sixth, the Chand study has suggested retention of a public agency to handle foodgrain trade, because in its absence private trade may turn exploitative.

Reduction of Farmers' Marketing Risks

Farmers face both yield and price risks. Yield or production risk can be covered by crop insurance and weather or rainfall insurance. For marketing risks, three instruments are available. One is MSP. Notwithstanding the effects in its implementation, it has helped a large number of farmers in surplus producing states to cover a part of their price risks. Effective implementation of MSP policy, as suggested earlier, will help farmers reduce their price risks.

A second instrument for covering price risk is the emerging scenario of contract farming arrangements, which are in a way future contracts on prices. There are several success stories relating to such arrangements. A precondition for contract farming to expand is amending state APMR legislation. This apart, a Model Contract has also been formulated and circulated to states. However, several complementary measures are needed for contract farming to expand on a large-scale. It will need (a) organization of farmers/producers groups; (b) legislation and effective implementation of a contract law; (c) improvement in the quality of input delivery and research and extension services; (d) training of farmers in maintenance of quality standards; (e) provision of complementary infrastructure, including IT kiosks (like e-choupal) in rural areas; and (f) development of an effective land record and administration system. This will also require identification of a group of villages for each niche commodity and provision of credit and incentives for the farmers to shift to the identified commodity.

A third instrument is the Farm Income Insurance Scheme (FIIS), introduced on a pilot scale in eighteen districts during Rabi 2003-04 and extended to one hundred districts of sixteen states during 2004-05. FIIS covers both price and yield risks. The scheme is compulsory for loanee farmers but optional for others. If successful, FIIS will replace the National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS) but NAIS will continue in uncovered districts. The government has announced a subsidy on premium up to 75% for marginal and small farmers and 50% for other farmers. The success of this laudable scheme will depend on the speed with which the estimates of area, yield and prices realized by the farmers are arrived at. These parameters both area at area and individual farmer's level are not easy to compile objectively. Further, the guaranteed level of income

is also based on indemnity of 80%, of moving average of seven years of actual yield. Statistically reliable yield estimates below the district level are not available and special yield estimation surveys at sub-district or lower levels have all the limitations of losing objectivity.

Farmers' Organization and Capacity Building

Farmers will benefit from deregulation of markets, minimum guaranteed price scheme, contract farming or crop/income insurance only to the extent organize in marketing groups, self-help groups, cooperatives or companies and learn skills suited to the new marketing environment. Understanding quality standards (including FAQ), learning the terms of contract and insurance, and choosing and preparing the produce for the market are going to be essential skills for farmers. State marketing departments, APMCs, marketing cooperatives, Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and PRIs should pay increasing attention to capacity building and organizing farmers for marketing in the new environment

Conclusion & Recommendations

- 1) The credit policy should continue to emphasize small borrowers. Commercial banks are way of lending for the priority sector and rural poor.
- 2) The provisions of mandatory lending to the agricultural activities should continue.
- 3) Banks should take the help of NGOs and local formal institutions in their lending programs to reduce transaction costs. These apart, effective linkages between farmers and other should be promoted. Interlocking of credit and product/input markets is crucial and should be recognized.
- 4) To meet the credit needs of the poor, programs like linking of self-help groups with lending agencies are important but in these linkages, the role of promoting institutions should not be lost sight of. Marketing and institutional credit systems have always remained critical for agricultural development. Their role has been enhanced in the liberalized economic environment.
- 5) The set of reforms and strategic actions suggested in this paper will help these systems strengthen Indian agriculture.
- 6) A statutory status should be assigned to the CACP and to its recommended MSPs to curb the tendency of fixing MSPs much above the rational level.
- 7) Instruments of price policy that have outlived their utility should be phased out. These are: (a) levy on rice millers; (b) levy on sugar factories; (c) state advised prices of sugarcane; (d) control on release of free-sale quota of sugar; and (e) monopoly procurement of raw cotton in Maharashtra.
- 8) Price support purchases of cereals should be decentralized to make price support effective in all states. Specifically, (a) in states like Punjab and should concentrate its efforts in states

where state agencies are not fully equipped and geared; and (c) price support operations and subsequent disposal of coarse cereals should be delegated to state governments, with financial back-up from the central government.

- 9) Targeted PDS has several positive features. Problems of leakage and subsidized grains not reaching the intended sections can be checked by publicizing the prices, list of targeted beneficiaries, and stock position of grains at fair price/ration shops and village panchayat offices and making gram panchayats or local bodies responsible for monitoring.

References

- 1) N L Agarwal (2004), "Agricultural Marketing in India", 4th edn, Oxford and IBH, New Delhi.
- 2) R L Jogi (2003), Minimum Support Prices in India: Some Issues, Working Paper No. 132, Institute of Development Studies, Jaipur, May.
- 3) Agarwal, N L and B L Meena (1997), "Agricultural Marketing in India – Performance of Cumin Marketing in Rajasthan", Bihar Journal of Agricultural Marketing, 5(3), September-December, pp.319-28.
- 4) Chand, Ramesh (2003), "Government Intervention in Foodgrain Markets in the New Context", Study Report prepared for the Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food and Public Distribution, Government of India, National Centre for Agricultural Economics and Policy Research, New Delhi, Policy Paper 19, March.
- 5) GOI (Government of India) (2004), The Economic Survey 2003-2004, Ministry of Finance, July.
- 6) (2002a), Report of Inter-Ministerial Task Force on Agricultural Marketing Reforms, Ministry of Agriculture, May.
- 7) www.nabard.org.in
- 8) www.rbi.org.in
- 9) www.ruralcredit.co.in

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